

Nutritional Therapy in the Treatment of Eosinophilic Esophagitis – Review of Current Guidelines and Dietary Management Strategy

**Agata Lewandowska¹, Magdalena Kartasińska-Kwaśnik², Aleksandra Gazi³,
Aleksandra Miszkurka⁴**

1. Agata Lewandowska [AL]

Bielański Hospital of Ks. J. Popiełuszko, Cegłowska 80, 01-809 Warsaw, Poland
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9008-1032>

2. Magdalena Kartasińska-Kwaśnik [MKK]

Freelancer
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-8275-4752>

3. Aleksandra Gazi [AG]

Freelancer
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-4519-914X>

4. Aleksandra Miszkurka [AM]

Bielański Hospital of Ks. J. Popiełuszko, Cegłowska 80, 01-809 Warsaw, Poland
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0295-5970>

Abstract

Eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) is a chronic immune-mediated disease with increasing prevalence, in which nutritional therapy plays a key therapeutic role. The most commonly used dietary intervention is the empirical six-food elimination diet (SFED), involving elimination of: cow's milk, wheat, soy, eggs, nuts, and fish/seafood. Current American College of Gastroenterology guidelines from 2025 suggest considering a step-up approach – starting with one-food elimination with possible expansion to SFED in case of non-response. The aim of this work is to review current guidelines on EoE diagnosis and treatment, and to present a dietary management strategy using a hypothetical clinical case of an adult female patient. Particular attention was paid to individualization of elimination diet considering potential cross-reactions with environmental allergens, which may determine tolerance of foods considered safe in standard SFED model. Detailed nutritional recommendations, tables of indicated and contraindicated products, and sample menu illustrating practical implementation of elimination diet while maintaining nutritional value and variety are presented.

Keywords: eosinophilic esophagitis, EoE, elimination diet, SFED, dietary therapy, cross-reactions

Introduction

Eosinophilic esophagitis (EoE) is a chronic immune-mediated disease [1; 2]. It is the most common form of primary eosinophilic gastrointestinal disorders (EGID), which also include eosinophilic gastritis and/or enteritis, and eosinophilic colitis [2]. The incidence and prevalence of EoE are increasing annually worldwide. Eosinophilic esophagitis occurs most frequently in North America, Western Europe, and Australia. It is estimated that in the United States, the prevalence of EoE is 40–90/100,000 people [3]. Noel et al. [4] estimated a 4-fold increase in the incidence of eosinophilic esophagitis in children between 2000–2003 in the United States.

The pathogenesis of eosinophilic esophagitis is not yet fully understood. Currently, EoE is recognized as an immune-mediated disease with a predominance of Th2 response, initiated by allergens that interact with a damaged esophageal mucosal barrier – either congenital or acquired – leading to recruitment of eosinophils and other effector cells, including mast cells, T lymphocytes, and basophils [6]. The most likely factors are believed to be genetic, environmental, and autoimmune [5].

Eosinophilic esophagitis is diagnosed in patients of all ages; it most commonly occurs in children between 5 and 10 years of age and adult men in their 3rd–4th decade of life [6; 7]. It is believed that men are more susceptible to this condition due to mutations in the X chromosome [6]. Coexistence of allergic diseases has been observed: urticaria, allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma, allergic eczema, and food allergies [3; 8; 9; 2]. Among patients diagnosed with EoE, elevated IgE antibody levels in serum and positive skin test results have been noted [6].

Mishra A. et al. [9] showed in a mouse study that exposure to *Aspergillus fumigatus* caused eosinophilia in the esophageal mucosa. This fungus is responsible for over 80% of fungal respiratory disorders and can act as an allergic, toxic, or infectious agent. Exposure to *A. fumigatus* occurs through inhalation of conidial spores and mycelial fragments penetrating the upper respiratory tract [10].

Clinical Presentation

The clinical presentation may vary depending on age. Most often, symptoms are nonspecific, which makes early diagnosis of EoE difficult [6]. In infants and young children, characteristic features include feeding difficulties, vomiting, and food aversion leading to growth disorders [6; 11]. In children, vomiting, abdominal pain, swallowing difficulties, and malnutrition dominate. In adults, the leading symptom is dysphagia with a sensation of food impaction in the esophagus, retrosternal pain, and odynophagia [12; 13; 7]. Many patients eliminate a large number of products from their diet due to swallowing difficulties [11].

Characteristic of EoE is inflammatory infiltrate with predominance of eosinophils and mast cells in the esophageal epithelium [12; 2]. The diagnosis is made when at least 15 eosinophils per high-power field (HPF) are found. In most patients, infiltrates involve the entire length of the esophagus. Endoscopic examination may reveal: esophageal rings, white exudates, furrows and folds of the mucosa, edema, and narrowing of the esophageal lumen [6].

Diagnostic Criteria for EoE – Current Guidelines

According to current American College of Gastroenterology guidelines from 2025 [11], which are an update of previous recommendations, the diagnosis of EoE is possible when the following criteria are met:

- Symptoms related to esophageal dysfunction are present (swallowing difficulties, sensation of food impaction, etc.)
- Eosinophilic infiltrate of at least 15 eosinophils/HPF has been confirmed in at least 6 biopsies from at least 2 esophageal levels
- Secondary causes of esophageal eosinophilia have been excluded: celiac disease, Crohn's disease, hypereosinophilic syndrome, achalasia, connective tissue diseases, reflux, eosinophilic gastritis/enteritis
- In endoscopic assessment, use of the EREFS scale (EoE Endoscopic Reference Score) is recommended, considering: edema, rings, exudates, furrows, and strictures

A significant change from the 2013 guidelines is the abandonment of the requirement to conduct a trial of proton pump inhibitor (PPI) therapy as a condition for diagnosing EoE. In current guidelines, PPIs are treated as a therapeutic option – not as a diagnostic tool [11]. This change is based on evidence indicating that lack of remission after PPI therapy does not differentiate EoE from other esophageal diseases [6; 11].

Treatment

Treatment of EoE includes: corticosteroid therapy, implementation of elimination diet (empirical, elemental, or based on allergy test results), use of biological drugs, and esophageal dilation [1; 2; 12]. According to ACG 2025 guidelines, the primary goal of therapy is control of both the inflammatory and fibrostenotic components of the disease [11].

Elimination Diet Models

The most commonly used dietary intervention is the empirical six-food elimination diet (SFED), which involves elimination of: cow's milk protein, wheat, soy, eggs, nuts, and fish and seafood [1; 6; 14; 15]. Dietary treatment lasts 4–8 weeks, after which eliminated products are gradually and individually reintroduced under monitoring of clinical symptoms and histological findings.

Results from a multicenter randomized trial in 2023 (Kliwer et al. [18]) showed that the histological efficacy of elimination of cow's milk alone (1FED) was comparable to the efficacy of SFED in adult patients with EoE. Histological remission was achieved in 40% of patients using SFED and 34% using 1FED, and this difference was not statistically significant. A 2023 meta-analysis including 1,762 patients confirmed that less restrictive elimination diet models may be equally effective, supporting a step-up approach: from elimination of one component, with possible expansion to SFED in case of non-remission [11; 19].

The elemental diet, based on amino acid formulas with elimination of all food allergens, achieves the highest remission rates (>90%), but due to low patient tolerance often requires feeding through a tube [15]. Both the applied diet and corticosteroid treatment may not bring expected effects in case of refractory EoE, exposing patients to esophageal remodeling with

strictures [7]. A study by Aceves SS. et al. [16] showed that EoE symptoms and esophageal remodeling may persist even after resolution of eosinophilia, suggesting involvement of eosinophil-independent pathways – mast cells and basophils – in esophageal dysfunction [7; 17].

Role of Eosinophils, Neutrophils, and Basophils in EoE Pathogenesis

In EoE, eosinophils (acidophilic granulocytes) play a key effector role. Upon activation, they release cytotoxic granule proteins – major basic protein (MBP), eosinophil peroxidase (EPO), eosinophil cationic protein (ECP), and eosinophil-derived neurotoxin (EDN) – which damage the esophageal epithelium, amplify the inflammatory response, and participate in tissue remodeling [7]. An increase in acidophilic granulocytes above normal (>5% leukocytes) is an expression of disease activity and a monitored indicator of treatment response.

Neutrophils (segmented granulocytes) play a secondary role in EoE, but their elevated count in peripheral blood may indicate accompanying chronic inflammation, infection, or exacerbation of the underlying disease. It is important to differentiate neutrophil increase as a nonspecific response from their direct involvement in EoE pathogenesis.

Basophils, constituting <1% of circulating leukocytes, participate in initiation and amplification of Th2-type allergic response. They release histamine, IL-4, and IL-13, which promote eosinophil recruitment and intensify IgE-dependent response. Mast cells and basophils can maintain esophageal dysfunction even after resolution of eosinophilia [7; 17].

Clinical Case Example

The following presents a hypothetical clinical example illustrating the application of empirical SFED diet in an adult female patient with EoE, developed based on current guidelines and the authors' experience in conducting nutritional therapy in this patient group.

Patient Characteristics and Clinical Presentation

A 40-year-old female patient with body weight of 68 kg before disease diagnosis, height 165 cm (BMI: 25 kg/m²). She presented to her primary care physician with symptoms of general weakness and diffuse abdominal pain intensifying after meals.

The patient was referred for gastroenterological examination, during which EoE was diagnosed based on endoscopic examination and histological assessment of esophageal mucosal biopsy. The gastroenterologist prescribed enteric-coated glucocorticosteroids and elimination diet and referred the patient for dietary consultation.

Medical history: the patient denied the presence of chronic diseases and had no previously known food allergies or intolerances. She had not previously performed allergy tests for IgE-dependent allergies, despite reporting symptoms after consuming many products.

Nutritional History and Nutritional Status Assessment

According to the nutritional history, the patient had eliminated from her diet: avocado, banana, kiwi, pineapple, mango, raspberries, blueberries, figs, persimmon, apricots, nuts, bell pepper, onion, goat cheese, and fish; she limited consumption of soft-boiled eggs and chocolate. According to the patient's subjective assessment, these products caused diffuse, persistent abdominal pain. She tolerated without symptoms: white bread, cold cuts, yellow cheese, tomatoes, cucumbers, radishes, strawberries, watermelon, apples, potatoes, and lentils.

For two weeks preceding the consultation, the patient significantly reduced meal intake due to intensification of pain after eating, which resulted in significant body weight loss (5 kg over 3 months) and intensification of fatigue symptoms.

Based on the food diary, an analysis of energy content and vitamin and mineral content of the diet was performed. The diet at that time was deficient in all nutrients. Prolonged use of a low-energy diet can lead to: body weight loss, malnutrition, deterioration of hair, skin and nail condition, impaired wound healing, increased inflammatory process, and worsening of treatment outcomes.

Laboratory Test Results

Basic anthropometric parameters were measured, showing progressive reduction in body weight in terms of both adipose and muscle tissue. Body weight at the time of dietary consultation was 63 kg (BMI: 23.1 kg/m²).

Complete blood count results showed the following parameters: WBC $7.28 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$; segmented granulocytes 43.7% (normal: 40–70%); eosinophils 13.7% (significantly elevated above normal 0.5–5%); MCV 86.7 fL (slightly decreased); MCHC 35.2 g/dL (slightly elevated). CRP was 8.2 mg/L (slightly elevated above normal <5 mg/L).

Morphological examinations showed elevated eosinophil count (13.7%), characteristic of active phase of EoE. The percentage of segmented granulocytes was within normal range, but at the upper limit, which may suggest accompanying chronic inflammation. Progressive decrease in MCV suggests developing iron or B-group vitamin deficiency as a consequence of long-term use of deficient diet. Elevated MCHC requires differential diagnosis for blood concentration or hemolysis.

Lipase level testing showed no pancreatic function disorders. Total IgA concentration was within normal range, which excluded the presence of intestinal parasites.

Nutritional Management

Diet Assumptions and Clinical Rationale

Due to lack of allergy test results, nutritional management in the form of empirical six-food elimination diet SFED was applied, including elimination of: dairy products, gluten-containing grains, legumes, eggs, nuts, and fish and seafood. The selection of eliminated product groups was based on standard SFED criteria, supplemented by individual assessment of patient tolerance and current pollen calendar, considering potential cross-reactions.

An important element of diet individualization was the exclusion of rice and rice flour despite their naturally gluten-free character. This decision resulted from considering the mechanism of cross-reactions between grass pollen allergens and rice proteins. This phenomenon is well documented – van Rhijn et al. showed that sensitization to birch and grass pollen with cross-reactivity to food allergens predominates in adult patients with EoE [20], and a 2023 study confirmed that SFED efficacy is significantly lower during pollen season in patients sensitized to birch and grass [21]. For this reason, alternative carbohydrate sources were used in the diet: millet, buckwheat, quinoa, and corn.

The second non-standard restriction concerned flaxseed, which was allowed only in ground form. Whole seed form (unground) may act mechanically irritating on the inflamed esophageal mucosa, which is a particularly important factor in patients with EoE, in whom the mucosa shows increased reactivity to mechanical stimuli and esophageal motility disorders [7]. Ground flaxseed retains nutritional values – it is a valuable source of omega-3 fatty acids, fiber, and lignans – while eliminating the risk of mechanical irritation.

Millet beverage was chosen as a cow's milk substitute due to low risk of cross-reactivity with grass allergens (unlike rice and oat beverage), absence of soy and almonds (which remain potential allergens in EoE), and good taste tolerance by the patient.

Caloric and Nutritional Implementation – Risk of Deficiencies

Due to the patient's prolonged use of unplanned elimination diet and significant body weight loss, the priority of dietary intervention was to meet energy and protein requirements while supplementing micronutrient deficiencies.

Initially, an attempt was made to include Modulen IBD supplement, which ended in intolerance manifested by nausea and abdominal discomfort after supplement intake. The next attempt was successful: Protifar (concentrated whey protein as protein supplementation) and Calogen (high-energy preparation based on plant fats) were included in the patient's diet for a period of 8 weeks. Supplementation enabled an increase in energy supply by approximately 400 kcal per day and protein by 20 g per day.

The applied elimination diet, in case of improper implementation, may lead to deficiencies of: calcium and vitamin D (dairy elimination), non-heme iron and B-group vitamins (elimination of legumes and gluten-containing grains), omega-3 fatty acids (fish elimination), as well as magnesium and zinc. During dietary care, special attention was paid to meal regularity, appropriate energy density of dishes, and supplementation of calcium (1000 mg/day) and vitamin D₃ (2000 IU/day).

Table 1. Indicated and contraindicated products in the applied elimination diet

Table 1 presents a detailed list of indicated and contraindicated products in the patient's diet, developed based on SFED assumptions with consideration of individual modifications resulting from assessment of cross-reaction risk with environmental allergens.

Product Group	Indicated	Contraindicated
Dairy	None	Cow's and goat's milk, dairy products (yogurts, buttermilk, kefir, cottage cheese, processed cheese, yellow cheese, feta, mozzarella, goat cheese), butter
Eggs	Possibly quail or duck eggs (for tolerance verification)	Chicken eggs
Grains	Corn, buckwheat, millet, amaranth, quinoa; flours and groats from above grains; gluten-free bread and pasta	Rice and rice flour (cross-reaction with grass pollen), wheat, triticale, barley, rye, regular oats; wheat and rice pasta
Meat	Poultry (chicken, turkey), rabbit, lean pork (ham, loin, tenderloin); poultry and pork cold cuts	Beef, veal, lamb, duck, goose, game; sausages, kabanos, frankfurters; highly processed cold cuts
Fish and seafood	None	All fish and seafood
Nuts and seeds	Ground flaxseed (only ground form)	All nuts, pumpkin seeds, sunflower seeds, poppy seeds, sesame, whole flaxseed
Fats	Plant margarine; oils: flaxseed, rapeseed, olive oil, sunflower	Butter, butter-margarine blends; soybean oil; fish fats (cod liver oil)
Fruits	Strawberries, currants (pureed), apples without skin, pears without skin, papaya, cherries, lemon, wild strawberries	Melon, watermelon, plums, blueberries, raspberries, peaches, apricots, mango, kiwi, banana, pineapple, persimmon, figs, dried fruits
Vegetables	Beetroot, cooked carrot, parsley, cucumber, lettuce, spinach, kale, pumpkin, potato, sweet potato, cauliflower, corn, cooked tomato, eggplant, zucchini	Bell pepper, onion, leek, broccoli, celery, raw tomato, raw carrot, cabbage, garlic, arugula; all legumes (beans, peas, chickpeas, lentils, soy, fava beans)

Beverages	Still water; infusions of chamomile, fennel, sage, lemon balm; green and white tea; grain coffee; millet beverage, buckwheat beverage	Carbonated water; carbonated drinks; fruit juices; natural coffee; nettle, mint infusions; rice, almond, oat, soy beverage
Spices	Oregano, basil, thyme, rosemary, marjoram, cumin, turmeric, sugar, salt, lemon juice, nutmeg, bay leaf, vanilla, cinnamon	Coriander, anise, caraway, curry, pepper, paprika, chili, ready spice mixes

It is recommended that products purchased in stores be as minimally processed as possible and contain the shortest list of ingredients, which will eliminate the risk of accidental consumption of contraindicated products (so-called hidden allergens).

Table 2. Sample one-day menu in SFED elimination diet

Table 2 presents sample dishes illustrating the method of implementing elimination diet while maintaining its variety and appropriate nutritional value.

Meal	Meal Suggestions
Breakfast / Dinner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Millet porridge from millet flakes (50 g) with millet beverage (200 ml), grated pear without skin and cinnamon • Sandwiches from gluten-free bread (buckwheat, corn) with margarine or olive oil, with poultry/pork cold cuts/tenderloin, additions: lettuce, cucumber, radish • Pancakes from millet flour with cherry or strawberry jam • Millet beverage with carob
Second breakfast / Afternoon snack	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salad: butter lettuce, cucumber without skin, 50 g roasted chicken breast, corn, olive oil and lemon dressing • Millet pudding: millet groats cooked in millet beverage with vanilla, blended, served with allowed fruits • Baked potatoes with rapeseed oil and herbs • Mix of cooked vegetables: carrot, parsley, cauliflower, corn

Lunch	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Clear soups based on vegetable broth (without celery and leek) with lean meat; addition: buckwheat groats, millet, quinoa, gluten-free pasta (not rice), potatoes• Spaghetti with gluten-free pasta (not rice), tomato sauce with olive oil and herbs, ground turkey meat• Lecso: stewed zucchini, pumpkin, eggplant with chicken/turkey, tomatoes. Spices: cumin, turmeric, oregano. Serve with quinoa, buckwheat or millet groats• Stewed dishes with chicken/turkey/rabbit with carrot and parsley in tomato sauce, with potatoes• Zucchini stuffed with ground turkey meat, quinoa/millet groats, zucchini, corn and tomatoes
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Nutritional Treatment Outcomes

After 6 weeks of SFED diet with protein-energy supplementation, the patient reported significant clinical improvement: reduction in pain, improved food tolerance, body weight increase of 2 kg (to 65 kg, BMI 23.9 kg/m²). Follow-up complete blood count showed a decrease in eosinophil percentage from 13.7% to 7.2%, suggesting partial suppression of the eosinophilic process. The patient continued the elimination diet for a total of 8 weeks before planned initiation of reintroduction phase of individual food groups under gastroenterologist supervision.

Discussion

The presented clinical case illustrates the multidimensional nature of diagnostic and nutritional challenges in EoE in an adult female patient. Spontaneous elimination of numerous products, conducted by the patient without specialist supervision, led to significant nutritional deficiencies and deterioration of nutritional status – a phenomenon well described in the literature. Wang et al. [1] showed that limited adherence to elimination diet and its independent modification constitute a significant barrier in long-term EoE therapy in adults.

The decision to apply empirical SFED diet resulted from lack of allergy test results, which is a situation not infrequently encountered in clinical practice. It is worth noting that skin prick tests have low predictive value in identifying allergens causing EoE – IgE-dependent tests predicted only 13% of foods significant in EoE pathogenesis [17]. This justifies the use of empirical elimination strategy instead of one directed by allergy test results.

A particularly important element of the described case was consideration of potential cross-reactions with environmental allergens during diet planning. Elimination of rice, despite its naturally gluten-free character, was dictated by the documented phenomenon of cross-reactivity with grass pollen [20; 21]. The study by van Rhijn et al. showed predominance of birch pollen sensitization with cross-reactivity to food allergens among adult patients with EoE, while the work of Lozano-Blasco et al. from 2023 confirmed that SFED is significantly less effective during pollen season in patients sensitized to grass and birch [21]. Consideration of pollen calendar in planning dietary intervention therefore seems to be an element of good clinical practice in this patient group.

It is worth noting the evolving approach to elimination diet model. A randomized clinical trial by Kliewer et al. from 2023 [18] showed comparable efficacy of 1FED and SFED with better patient tolerance of the less restrictive model. A meta-analysis from 2023 including 1,762 patients confirmed that a step-up approach – from elimination of one or two components – is clinically justified [11; 19]. In the described case, due to lack of available allergy test results and severe symptoms, it was decided to apply full SFED diet as first-line management.

The decrease in eosinophil percentage from 13.7% to 7.2% after 6 weeks of SFED observed in laboratory tests suggests partial response to dietary treatment. Persistence of elevated values above normal indicates the need to continue therapy and consider further management modifications. Slight decrease in MCV and increase in MCHC may reflect developing iron or B-group vitamin deficiencies, which emphasizes the importance of systematic monitoring of laboratory parameters and supplementation of deficits during long-term use of elimination diet.

Conclusions

Eosinophilic esophagitis is a chronic immune-mediated disease in which nutritional management constitutes an integral element of treatment. The presented case indicates the need to include a dietitian in the multidisciplinary therapeutic team already at the diagnosis stage – before the patient develops significant nutritional deficiencies secondary to spontaneous, unplanned eliminations.

Planning elimination diet in EoE should consider not only standard allergen groups covered by SFED, but also the individual environmental sensitization profile of the patient. Cross-reactions with pollen allergens (grass, birch) may determine tolerance of seemingly safe products, such as rice, which justifies modification of the standard diet model. Consideration of pollen calendar in planning and assessing the effectiveness of dietary intervention seems to be an element of good clinical practice.

In accordance with current ACG guidelines from 2025 [11] and results of randomized trials [18], it is reasonable to consider starting dietary therapy from less restrictive models with possibility of gradual expansion of elimination scope. Regardless of the adopted model, key importance is attached to: patient education in safe implementation of elimination diet, regular monitoring of nutritional status and laboratory parameters, and assessment of therapeutic adherence.

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Investigation: [AM], [AL], [AG]

Resources: [AL], [AG], [MKK]

Data curation: [AM], [AL]

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